

Relationship between ShB disease development, $\logit \times$ (HRLH%) and time with different inoculum sources on IR64, IR72, and IR26957-86-2 in the screenhouse.

plants were sprayed weekly with triphenyltin acetate at 1 kg formulated product/ha, no disease developed. Infected rice stem inoculum differed significantly from the other inoculum sources and produced the lowest area

under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) in all three cultivars and for all sources of inoculum. The three other inoculum sources were equally effective for ShB development under screenhouse conditions.

Among cultivars, highly susceptible IR72 had significantly higher AUDPC in response to mycelial inoculum. Cultivars IR64 and IR72 did not differ significantly in response to rice grain-hull and sclerotia inocula but had significantly higher AUDPC than IR26957-86-2. There were no varietal differences in response to rice stem inoculum.

The regression analysis of ShB development ($\logit \times$) with time for different inoculum treatments on the three cultivars are presented in the figure.

The regression coefficient or apparent infection rate (r)/unit per day for all inoculum sources was 0.0482 for IR64, 0.0759 for IR72, and 0.0530 for IR26957-86-2. However, mycelia, rice grain-hull, and sclerotia had similar r , which were higher than that for rice stem inoculum source in all cultivars. The R^2 value for the cultivars ranged from 0.75 to 0.78.

IR72 had the highest r , followed by IR64 and IR26957-86-2. This confirms that IR72 is more susceptible than the two other cultivars, regardless of inoculation method. ■

Effect of rice growth stage on sheath blight (ShB) development and yield loss

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To determine the effect of time of ShB infection on disease development and yield loss, we inoculated rice cultivars IR42 and IR72 with *Rhizoctonia solani* grown on a rice grain-hull mixture (rice:hull = 1:3) at tillering, panicle initiation, booting, and flowering during 1989 dry season.

Percent infected tillers and the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) scale were used to score disease development in 24 hills from 8- × 4-m plots at 5-d intervals up to 6 times. At maturity, 20 randomly selected plants from each plot were harvested and their yield components measured. A 2- × 1-m

area from the center of each plot was harvested to measure yield per hectare. Disease progress curves of each treatment were used to calculate area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC).

Highly significant differences in AUDPC were found between treatments and between cultivars (Table 1). In IR42, inoculation at flowering ranked first (AUDPC value 1958.06). Inoculation at panicle initiation had the lowest AUDPC (1622.13).

In IR72, AUDPC at flowering and panicle initiation stages were significantly higher than those at tillering and booting. Among growth stages, tillering had the lowest AUDPC. IR42 had significantly higher AUDPC than IR72 at all growth stages except panicle initiation.

The results indicate that rice is more susceptible at booting and flowering than at tillering and panicle initiation.

In IR42, AUDPC based on SES scale showed no significant differences

between treatments. Inoculation at tillering stage gave the lowest AUDPC value (62.00).

Table 1. Area under disease progress curve (AUDPC) based on disease incidence (%) and SES scale for 2 rice cultivars inoculated at different growth stages, 1988-89.^a

Growth stage	AUDPC	
	IR42	IR72
<i>Percent disease incidence</i>		
Tiller	1651.50 cx	1465.25 cy
Panicle initiation	1622.13 cy	1692.75 ax
Booting	1727.38 bx	1588.06 by
Flowering	1958.06 ax	1735.44 ay
Control	0.00 dx	0.00 dx
CV (%)		
Cultivar - 2.7		
Treatment - 3.0		
<i>SES</i>		
Tiller	62.00 ax	51.94 cy
Panicle initiation	63.31 ax	61.06 bx
Booting	62.31 ax	63.44 abx
Flowering	65.94 ax	65.31 ax
Control	0.00 dx	0.00 dx
CV (%)		
Cultivar - 4.1		
Treatment - 5.2		

^a Mean of 4 replications. Means followed by a common letter in a column (a, b, c, d) or in a row (x, y) are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

There was no cultivar difference except at tillering.

Effect on yield components of different treatments are presented in Table 2. Percent productive tillers and grain weight per plant were highest in control plots and lowest with inoculation at booting in both IR42 and IR72.

Filled grain number per panicle did not significantly differ among treatments in both IR42 and IR72, but there were significant differences in 1000-grain weight, filled grain percentage, and total biomass per plant.

Control had the highest biomass/plant, followed by tillering and panicle initiation, in both the cultivars. Inoculated plants had the lowest biomass values at booting and flowering, but IR42 and IR72 did not differ significantly. Inoculations at booting and flowering produced the lowest yield parameters.

Yields ranged from 3.8 to 5.6 t/ha in IR42 and from 3.7 to 5.6 t/ha in IR72.

Table 2. Yield components and yield loss in 2 rice cultivars inoculated at different growth stages, 1988-89.^a

Treatment	Productive tillers (%)	Grain wt/plant (g)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	1000-grain weight (g)	Filled grains (%)	Total biomass/plant (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)
<i>IR42</i>								
Tillering	89.30 b	18.22 ab	49.00 a	17.98 ab	72.90 a	50.68 a	4.2 b	24.01 a
Panicle initiation	81.30 bc	17.10 b	46.00 a	17.60 bc	72.80 a	49.20 a	4.2 b	23.08 a
Booting	79.00 c	12.98 c	47.00 a	16.53 c	62.80 b	39.18 b	4.2 b	23.01 a
Flowering	87.50 b	16.15 b	46.00 a	18.13 a	64.80 b	42.50 b	3.8 b	32.15 a
Control	100.00 a	20.45 a	51.00 a	19.13 a	76.30 a	52.48 a	5.6 a	
<i>IR72</i>								
Tillering	91.30 b	21.97 b	41.00 a	23.75 a	71.2 b	46.70 ab	4.9 b	13.53 b
Panicle initiation	88.50 b	17.50 c	42.00 a	22.15 b	69.90 bc	42.00 bc	4.8 b	15.40 b
Booting	83.80 b	13.83 d	37.00 ab	21.73 bc	63.80 cd	42.40 bc	4.4 b	21.05 b
Flowering	89.30 b	12.98 d	28.00 b	20.68 c	62.00 d	37.95 c	3.7 c	34.83 a
Control	99.90 a	24.95 a	41.00 a	24.25 a	82.60 a	54.20 a	5.6 a	
CV (%)								
Cultivar	10.6	16.5	13.5	6.8	13.2	17.5	7.2	61.7
Treatment	6.2	10.6	14.2	3.8	7.0	9.4	9.6	30.0

^a Mean of 4 replications. In a column, mean followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Yields of control plots were significantly higher. In both cultivars, inoculation at flowering resulted in the lowest yields and highest yield loss.

Yield loss due to ShB may occur at any stage, but is higher when infection occurs at booting or flowering. ■

Comparison of rice sheath blight (ShB) assessment methods

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We evaluated five methods for assessing ShB on three rice cultivars—highly susceptible IR72, susceptible IR64, and moderately resistant IR26957-86-2—in a pot experiment in the screenhouse during 1989 dry season. The methods were highest relative lesion height (HRLH %), disease severity (DS %), disease incidence (DI %), *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES), and real area infected (RAI %). RAI % was calculated by measuring the length and width of infected area.

Rice plants (5/pot) were inoculated with *Rhizoctonia solani* grown on rice grain-hull mixture (rice:hull = 1:3) at booting. Disease development was measured at 3-d intervals from inoculation, up to eight times. The area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC) was used to compare the three cultivars.

All assessment methods except DI gave the lowest AUDPC value in IR26957-86-2, confirming that IR26957-86-2 was more resistant to ShB infection than either IR64 or IR72 (see table).

All methods showed variable results among cultivars and also within each cultivar at different times of assessment (see table and figure).

Assessment by HRLH (%) is easy but tedious because each tiller in a hill must be evaluated.

Estimation of percent leaf and sheath area infected (DS) was faster than HRLH % and more efficient for evaluating a large amount of material within a short time. Assessment by DI showed that all tillers in a hill were infected within a few days of inoculation. But this method does not give total infection or an accurate assessment of DS—important data in epidemiological and yield loss studies.

ShB assessment by SES scale was easy and quick, but that method does not give a quantitative measure of real infection. For

AUDPC and standard error of 5 assessment methods applied to 3 rice cultivars, measured in a screenhouse experiment, 1988-89.^a

Method	AUDPC		
	IR64	IR72	IR26957-86-2
HRLH (%)	861.86 bx ± 29.00 (6.7)	828.11 bx ± 56.10 (13.5)	545.78 by p 31.50 (11.5)
DS (%)	437.81 cx ± 30.50 (14.0)	424.88 cx ± 19.30 (9.1)	317.63 cy p 51.20 (32.1)
DI (%)	2086.88 ax ± 1.88 (0.2)	2068.13 ax ± 12.25 (1.2)	2082.00 ax p 6.36 (0.6)
SES (0-9)	90.60 dx ± 5.20 (11.5)	85.91 ex ± 7.95 (17.6)	68.55 dx p 9.60 (28.1)
RAI (%)	386.01 cx ± 24.22 (12.7)	347.29 dxy ± 20.15 (11.6)	294.67 cy p 10.01 (6.7)

^a Mean of 4 replications. Means followed by a common letter in a column (a, b, c) or in a row (x, y, z) are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Figures within parentheses indicate CV (%).